

NDAC/LO/095

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, V.

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1. Introduction

In a series of previous notes, the reduction methods to be used for binary and multiple stars have been developed. A summary was presented at the 3:rd FAST thinkshop in Bari (NDAC/LO/085.1), and it appeared then that few major problems remained. These "old" results are based on detailed observation simulations that were thought to be fully realistic in essence, even if they did not follow the actual reduction schemes in detail.

The "real" reduction process for binary and multiple stars is now rather well-defined, however, as described by Lindegren in another Bari-paper (NDAC/LO/090). The present report describes new double star simulations that follow this scheme in more detail. It appears that there are unexpected problems for some categories of doubles, which possibly necessitate some changes in the proposed processing.

2. Two-stage simulation

The "old" double star simulations are described most fully in the first report of this series (NDAC/LO/066). The major parts of the SCAN and SAMP modules are used in the present runs also, with the following important modifications:

- 1) In SCAN, more realistic attitude deviations are used, as obtained by Lindegren. A bimodal distribution is now used for $\ddot{\Omega}$ (gaussian peaks at -0.004 and $+0.009$ arcsec/s²), and the angular rate standard deviation is set at 1.2 arcsec/s.
- 2) Instead of using SCAN-data for only a few "standard" positions on the sky, each run now has new RA,dec (chosen usually at random to give an input ecliptic latitude). This gives a realistic distribution of scan-geometries, with eclipses by the earth and the moon taken into account.

- 3) In SAMP, the field-coordinates are no longer linearly interpolated over a whole frame, but only over each (16 times shorter) interlacing period. Otherwise, the later "phase-calibration" at frame mid-times becomes erroneous with a (generally) non-linear attitude motion.
- 4) Stellar aberration is now included (with a simple, circular geostationary orbit for the satellite), but for simplicity (due to its smallness), the gravitational light-deflexion is neglected.
- 5) The output from SAMP is no longer directly the b-parameters as used in the solution programs, but the β -parameters as derived in the normal preprocessing. These betas are calculated for each frame, but the basic idea (cf. NDAC/LO/090) is to average all except the phase β_3 over each FOV (8 whole frames). The weights for this averaging are proportional to the 33-element in the β information matrices, cf. NDAC/LO/076, where the total output for each FOV-passage is specified.

In the first stage of the new simulations, the β -parameters (and their information matrix) are output for each FOV-passage in one output-file, and in another the "true" simulated attitudes are saved. The β -output is as obtained in the real preprocessing, and in the second stage of the simulations, one has to "calibrate" these data, using information available only after the main reductions are completed. This second simulation step is straightforward but new, and gives as final output the Case History File as described in NDAC/LO/090.

2. The CHF-derivation

The key process in deriving a CHF is the phase-calibration. In the regular preprocessing, the reference-phase is simply set to zero at each frame mid-time, and in the calibration one has now to derive the "absolute" phases for the frame mid-times. Absolute here means that it is referred to an arbitrary "reference point" described by its five astrometric parameters. (In most cases, the reference point is simply the Input Catalogue position, proper motion and parallax, for the primary star or the photocentre of the system).

For this known position on the sky, we may now calculate an almost rigorous proper direction at each frame mid-time. The observations are made from the spinning satellite, however, and we need also the best available

attitude estimates. In the simulations, the true attitudes were saved, and over a FOV-passage, one assumes OGAR values for the heliotropic angles ξ , ν , Ω (and their derivatives $\dot{\xi}$, $\dot{\nu}$, $\dot{\Omega}$, $\ddot{\Omega}$) equal to the true ones plus gaussian errors. The standard deviations are usually taken to be 0.11, 0.15, 0.003 arcsec, 3.2, 5.0, 0.1 mas/sec, and 0.01 mas/sec/sec respectively, as obtained in realistic simulations by Lindegren. From tests with other values, the accuracy in the phase-calibrations is determined mainly by σ_{Ω} , that is, by the accuracy of the "along-scan" attitude determined in the Great-Circle Reductions. (Note that Step 1 results alone are not sufficient; one has to apply also the set zero-point errors as determined only in the Sphere Reconstitution).

The satellite attitude plus the proper direction to the reference point gives the field coordinates (w_0, z_0) , which are then transformed via known instrument parameters to a calculated grid-coordinate G_0 . This G_0 is a best estimate for the reference-point grid-coordinate at frame mid-time, and the difference

$$\Delta = \beta_3 - 2\pi G_0 \quad (1)$$

(observed - reference phase at frame mid-time) should be approximately constant over the whole FOV-passage. This is tested simply by calculating an empirical Δ -variance for each FOV-passage, and then comparing it with the expected β_3 -variance from the information-matrix. In most cases, the variances are very similar, but as explained in Section 4 below, there are important exceptions.

With the phases thus "calibrated", the β -values from the preprocessing may be transformed to b -values as required by the solution-programs. The beta information-matrices F_{β} are similarly transformed to F_b , (cf. NDAC/LO/090, eqs. 10,11). For each FOV-passage, one has now the main "observations" b_1 - b_5 , together with their (nearly diagonal) information matrix.

In order to set up the requisite observation equations in the subsequent solution programs, one has also to have the exact scan-geometry at each FOV-passage. As explained by Lindegren in NDAC/LO/090, it is possible to define "standard coordinates" (in a small area around a tangential point close to the reference point), that includes the effects of differential aberration. Using such xy -coordinates, one may calculate differential coefficients A_x , A_y , P , such that the phase relative to the reference phase is given simply by

$$dph = A_x (x-x_0) + A_y (y-y_0) + P (\pi-\pi_0) \quad (2)$$

where x_0, y_0, π_0 are of course the x, y and parallax for the reference point.

3. The solution program

For simplicity, the "old" solution programs are changed only as far as to be able to cope with the new observation-format. The most important change is in the accumulation of the normal equations, where now the full b information matrix is used in the weighting instead of only the b variances. That is, instead of adding for each FOV the contribution

$$\Delta a(i,j) = \sum_{k=1}^5 dif(k,i)*dif(k,j)*wt(k) \quad (3)$$

to the NE coefficient $a(i,j)$, we now add

$$\Delta a(i,j) = \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{l=1}^5 dif(k,i)*dif(l,j)*F_b(k,l) \quad (4)$$

(Theoretically, this is the "best" weighting, when one knows the full F_b matrix. In practice, the final gain in accuracy is very minor, as would be expected from the near diagonal F_b). The important weight-corrections due to the IFOV-profile, as described in NDAC/LO/067, are made only on the diagonal elements of F_b , with the inter- b correlations unchanged.

In the "old" runs it was also possible to change the a priori positional knowledge when starting a solution. Now, an "Input Catalogue"-position is simulated already when the observations are generated, (normally at 1.25 arcsec from the true one), and the "grid-iteration" for the primary position is tested only for this single offset. It is always possible, however, to get the final converged solution by starting the least squares solution with the true parameter values.

In most cases, the new solution program gives results that are very similar to the old ones. To be able to compare in more detail, it is necessary to have data for exactly similar object- and scan-geometries. The obvious method to accomplish this is to make a simultaneous simulation/solution along the old and the new lines. In SAMP, the old (b)

observation-file is produced together with the new (β) data. The β data are then phase-calibrated and transformed back to the CHF b-file, and one has then two sets of b-data that should be almost identical. Some gross inconsistencies were identified and corrected at this stage, but generally, the comparison is between the final ("old" and "new") solutions. As before, the main measure of the quality of a solution is the single quantity rms(comp), giving the equal weight rms deviation for all five astrometric parameters. It is also useful to check the chisquare fit of the (O-C):s, S, which with correct weighting should average 4 times the number of FOV-passages (because only b_2 - b_5 are used in the final LS-iterations).

Rather consistently, both the "new" rms-values and the new S-values are some 20% higher than the old ones. The rms-increase is mostly due to the attitude uncertainty introduced in the CHF-calibration, but in individual cases, this influence is rather complex. Table 1 shows results for three sets of observations (A: 8.5+10.0, sep=1"; B: 8.5+11.5, sep=5"; C: 8.5+8.5, sep=15"), where the CHF calibration and solution has been repeated 10 times for different specified σ_Ω .

Table 1. Means and std deviations of solution rms-values for 10 runs at each σ_Ω . [All values in mas].

σ_Ω	A				B				C	
	<pr>	σ	<sec>	σ	<pr>	σ	<sec>	σ	<p+s>	σ
0	1.01	.04	4.54	.06	.76	.04	16.4	.3	2.84	.02
2	1.03	.15	4.57	.08	.77	.19	17.1	.7	2.87	.14
4	1.21	.25	4.66	.30	1.06	.22	17.3	1.6	2.94	.23
7	1.50	.32	5.03	.48	1.26	.31	16.4	2.9	2.96	.54
10	1.74	.56	5.20	1.00	1.81	.86	15.4	5.2	3.43	.57

The definite and expected effect of an increased attitude uncertainty is an increased spread in the solution rms-values. The increase in the mean rms-values is not very apparent for small σ_Ω , but a roughly linear relation may possibly be fitted. (It seems clear that the rms-values for the primary and the secondary component increase by approximately equal amounts, perhaps contrary to expectation). With a "typical" rms-increase of about 0.05-0.10 mas for each mas in σ_Ω , the 3 mas σ_Ω as used in the present simulations explains most of the increased solution errors.

An interesting datum is also the relation between the actual errors and the formal errors given by the inverse NE matrix. This is specified e.g. by the chisquare parameter S_e (squared sum of the actual over the mean error for the five astrometric parameters), which should have a mean value equal to 5. For a "random" collection of 120 systems (with separations from 0.5-15 arcsec, magnitude differences from 0-3, and positions at all ecliptic latitudes), I have checked the mean S_e . For the "old" solutions, this mean is 5.2 ± 0.3 for both the primaries and the secondaries (which is really better than expected). For the "new" solutions, the value is 7.5 for the primaries, 7.3 for the secondaries, with a mean error around 0.5. These numbers are again consistent with a 20% error-increase for the new runs.

4. The problem cases

So far, everything seems OK, but then there turned up a serious problem for certain doubles with nearly equal components. As can be readily seen from the standard superposition formulae for the Fourier b-parameters, two equal components separated by one half slit-period will have the first-harmonic parameters b_2 and b_3 close to zero. This means β_2 will be small, the phase (β_3) poorly determined, and β_4 and β_5 very large. Observations like these will have to be given lower weight, because they show up in the CHF-calibration with a Δ -spread much larger than expected from the β_3 theoretical variance given by the information matrix. For separations about 0.6-0.8 arcsec this is rather serious, because many scan-angles will give the half-slit apparent separation. At low ecliptic latitudes, the scan-pattern is in two dominant directions, and for some object position angles, most of the observations will be affected.

A natural remedy would seem to be to base the CHF phase calibration on the second harmonic phase instead, for these critical FOV:s. Unfortunately, this means that two alternative definitions of the β -parameters will have to be used, the second one being

$$\text{IDT count} \sim \beta_1 + \beta_2 [\cos(2*(H+\beta'_3)) + \beta'_4 * \cos(H+\beta'_3) + \beta'_5 * \sin(H+\beta'_3)] \quad (5)$$

There are two problems with this approach. First, a given second harmonic phase ($2*\beta'_3$) corresponds to two different β'_3 -values, separated by 180° . This means in practice that only b_4 and b_5 may be unambiguously determined in the

CHF-calibration, (but since b_2 and b_3 are small anyway, this is not serious). Secondly, it may be difficult to specify a priori which β -definition should be used in each FOV. In the preprocessing, one will have to determine β_1 - β_5 plus β'_2, β'_3 for each frame (because β'_4 and β'_5 will be useless in the end), and the output from a FOV will then be averages of $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_4, \beta_5$ and β'_2 , plus individual (frame-wise) β_3 and β'_3 . (Only the standard information matrix F_β is needed, as derived from β_1 - β_5).

Assuming that these data are available for each FOV (which will increase the necessary storage space for the whole mission from 2000 to 2500 Mb), an "optimum" set of (b) observations is defined as follows:

- 1) When the ratio (fsig) between the observed and the expected spread in the first harmonic Δ -values is below some preset limit sigl, the standard conversion from β_1 - β_5 to b_1 - b_5 is effected.
- 2) When fsig is greater than sigl, b_2 and b_3 are derived in the standard way, b_4 and b_5 from the alternative β' -values. No changes are made in the weighting (F_β).

For comparison, a "best" standard solution (with only β_1 - β_5 available) is obtained by reducing F_β for b_4 and b_5 by the factor $fr/fsig^2$ whenever fsig is greater than sigl. The parameter sigl may be chosen rather freely in the approximate range 1-2, but the value 1.2 has mostly been used. The parameter fr was originally optimised to 1.0, and all results below are for this standard value. From runs with different fr, I think now that $fr=0.1$ may be a better choice. (Statistically, the rms-values may thus be decreased by about 10%, but with individual solutions showing very different behaviour when fr is varied).

To summarize, after some optimizations, I have arrived at two alternative "new" solutions ('N1' using only the standard betas, 'N2' using β'), which are to be compared to the "old" solutions and with each other. (Note that the old solutions have no half-slit problems, because the phase is always rigorously referred to the reference position). The question to be answered is simply how superior the N2 solution is in these critical cases, as compared with the "standard" N1 one.

In trying to answer this question, I have made test-runs for many equal-magnitude systems, but because of their 1-2 hour CPU demand each, they are still too few to give really satisfactory statistics. Usually, I have specified the component magnitudes and separation, and the ecliptic latitude, and then made 10-20 runs (simulation + solution). The solution rms-values vary a lot from system to system, and for an individual case, the rms-ratios

between different (N1,N2, old) solutions are impossible to use. For a whole series, however, one may form mean rms-values, and the ratios between such means may be significant. Table 2 gives some results for the "bad" separation 0.7 arcsec, and Table 3 shows the mean dependence on the separation for low-latitude 8.5+8.5 systems.

Table 2. Mean rms-values (mas, mean error in parentheses), for n systems of equal-magnitude stars at 0.7 arcsec separation and at different ecliptic latitudes. 'O' stands for "old" solution, 'N1' for "standard" new solution, and 'N2' is an "optimum" new solution.

H-mag	lat($^{\circ}$)	n	O	N1	N2	N1/O	N2/O
6.0	6	21	0.7(.1)	1.5(.1)	1.3(.1)	2.1	1.8
6.0	17	18	0.6(.0)	1.2(.1)	1.0(.1)	2.1	1.8
6.0	30	18	0.6(.0)	1.1(.1)	0.9(.1)	1.9	1.6
8.5	6	33	1.1(.1)	2.3(.1)	1.6(.1)	2.0	1.4
8.5	17	18	1.2(.1)	2.0(.1)	1.4(.1)	1.8	1.2
8.5	30	22	.9(.1)	1.4(.1)	1.1(.1)	1.6	1.3
11.0	6	23	4.2(.2)	10.7(.6)	6.7(.3)	2.6	1.6
11.0	17	18	3.0(.2)	7.9(.6)	6.0(.2)	2.7	2.0
11.0	30	18	2.9(.2)	8.0(.5)	5.8(.3)	2.7	2.0
11.0	44	18	2.2(.1)	5.0(.3)	3.8(.3)	2.3	1.7
11.0	64	18	2.0(.1)	5.8(.4)	3.8(.2)	2.9	1.9

Table 3. Mean rms-values (mas, mean errors in parentheses) for 8.5+8.5 systems at ecliptic latitude 6° for different separations.

Sep(")	n	O	N1	N2	N1/O	N2/O	fp
0.5	10	1.5(.2)	1.8(.2)	1.7(.2)	1.2	1.1	0.00
0.6	10	1.1(.1)	2.2(.2)	1.5(.1)	1.9	1.4	0.28
0.65	20	1.2(.1)	2.5(.2)	1.6(.1)	2.1	1.3	0.37
0.7	33	1.1(.1)	2.3(.1)	1.6(.1)	2.0	1.4	0.23
0.8	10	1.1(.1)	1.8(.1)	1.4(.1)	1.6	1.3	0.15
1.0	10	1.3(.1)	2.0(.2)	1.8(.2)	1.5	1.3	0.10
1.5	10	1.2(.1)	1.6(.1)	1.5(.1)	1.3	1.3	0.06
1.7	10	1.4(.1)	1.5(.1)	1.5(.1)	1.1	1.0	0.05
1.85	10	1.2(.1)	2.7(.4)	1.7(.1)	2.3	1.4	0.25
2.5	8	1.6(.2)	2.0(.2)	1.8(.2)	1.2	1.1	0.08
3.0	10	1.3(.1)	1.8(.2)	1.5(.1)	1.4	1.2	0.16
6.0	10	1.4(.2)	1.9(.2)	1.6(.2)	1.3	1.1	0.09
9.0	10	1.4(.1)	2.3(.3)	1.6(.1)	1.7	1.2	0.08
10.0	10	1.6(.1)	2.0(.2)	1.8(.1)	1.3	1.1	0.08

At first, I thought that only a small interval of separations (0.6-1 arcsec) would show the problem, but as seen in Table 3, high N/O-ratios are observed for large separations also. This is indeed quite natural, as may be seen from the following simple model. For a uniform distribution of scan-angles over a double of separation ρ , a fraction f_p will give apparent separations within ds from half-integer values of the slit-period (sp). From the geometry, there follows at once

$$f_p = (2/\pi) \sum \left\{ \arccos \left[\frac{((i+0.5)*sp-ds)}{\rho} \right] - \arccos \left[\frac{((i+0.5)*sp + ds)}{\rho} \right] \right\} \quad (6)$$

where the sum is continued as long as $(i+0.5)*sp+ds < \rho$. This is a "sawtooth"-curve with teeth at separations close to $(i+0.5)*sp$. For smaller/larger ds , the teeth are narrower/broader, and the whole curve is shifted downwards/upwards. For very large separations, the limit of f_p is simply $2*(ds/sp)$.

Instead of looking only at the solutions close to 0.7 arcsec separation, we have to try to correlate the N/O-values with the f_p -values. This can not be done very strictly, because it is difficult to choose an "effective" ds -value. In Table 3, the f_p -values calculated with $ds=0.06$ arcsec are shown in the last column, and we see indeed a definite correlation with large f_p leading to large N/O. Very approximately, we may give these relations as

$$\begin{aligned} N1/O &= 1.1 + 3*f_p \\ N2/O &= 1.1 + f_p \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Eqs. (7) are derived from the data for 8.5-mag pairs at low ecliptic latitude, but they are probably typical for other cases too (with fainter stars having a larger slope, high-latitude ones a smaller one).

There exists thus several separation-intervals where the solutions for equal-magnitude doubles have mean errors that are significantly increased relative to the "old" runs. The "optimum" N2 solution is certainly better than the "standard" N1, but part of the rms-increase always remains. In other runs, I have checked the dependence on the magnitude difference: the effect seems mostly gone at $\Delta m=0.5$ although most of it remains at $\Delta m=0.25$. This is roughly consistent with the ds -value used above, because a deviation of 0.06 arcsec (18° in phase) from the half-slit position means an amplitude reduction by some $\sin(18^\circ)=30\%$.

Like for the "normal" cases, I have checked also the S and S_e -values. The LS fit to the observations, S , turns out to be a useable measure of the quality of a solution. Statistically, we may use the ratio $S/(4*nfov)$ as a good estimate of the rms-increase. The S_e -values are correspondingly enlarged, showing (as expected) that the formal mean errors do not indicate the true errors.

5. Number of systems affected

In order to appreciate the seriousness of the problem defined above, it is necessary to have at least a rough estimate of the number of equal-magnitude doubles in the critical ranges of separation. The final Input Catalogue is not yet available, but there exists a preliminary version (IC1, INCA, Feb 1987) that gives some guidance. The double star data are incomplete, with magnitude differences given only for the wide pairs ($sep > 10$ arcsec), and with separations only to the nearest arcsec. For our rough purposes, we assume a flat Δm -distribution between 0 and 3.5, and assume thus that about 1/7 of the close systems in IC1 have $\Delta m < 0.5$.

Using now eq. (7), we may transform a theoretical $fp(sep)$ -relation into a semi-empirical $N/O(sep)$ -relation. The large N/O -values come at narrow $lg sep$ intervals, and summing these, we may estimate the total numbers of "equal-magnitude" doubles with problems in the separation-range 0.5-10 arcsec. (At larger separations, the individual pointing introduces an effective magnitude-difference even between equal components, and the amplitude of the fp -curve is also diminished). The final result shown in Table 4 is admittedly based on several uncertain assumptions, but it is thought to give at least the gross quantitative features of the problem.

Table 4. Approximate numbers of double stars with $\Delta m < 0.5$ and with different expected amounts of error-increase (N/O) for the standard ($N1$) or optimum ($N2$) solutions.

Solution	N/O	<1.3	1.3-1.5	1.5-1.7	1.7-1.9	>1.9
N1		150	500	120	40	40
N2		770	80	0	0	0

Keeping in mind that the total number of binaries with $\text{sep} < 10$ arcsec is at least some 7500, the problem-cases are still relatively few. The decision to be taken is whether a significantly increased accuracy for a few hundred systems is worth the extra preprocessing and storage required for the N2 solution.

Previously, (as long as I thought that only separations close to 0.7 arcsec were affected), I thought the answer was no. The figures in Table 4 do however speak for the N2 solution, because the only real "difficulty" is the extra storage of preprocessing results required. The actual preprocessing is not significantly altered, it is only a matter of calculating

$$\beta_2 = \text{sqrt}(b_4^{**2} + b_5^{**2}) \tag{8}$$

$$\beta_3 = 0.5 * \text{atan}(-b_5/b_4)$$

from the b_4 and b_5 already available, and then averaging β_2 together with $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_4$ and β_5 . (An "alternative" information-matrix would have the same 33 element, thus the standard weights are correct).

If the "double" preprocessing results gives storage or administrative problems, I have checked an "intermediate" solution type, where the amplitude-ratio β_2/β_3 determines which set of parameters (β or β') that is forwarded from the preprocessing. At the solution-stage, the remaining cases of large f_{sig} are weighted as in the N1-solution. From some test-series, it appears that a solution closer to N2 than to N1 may be obtained by a suitable choice of weighting. (Only the most obvious problem-FOV:s with $\beta_2/\beta_3 < 0.25$ should have the β' output, for the rest, a reduced weight for b_4, b_5 would be enough).

6. Conclusion

For most doubles, the present (more realistic) simulations give results quite comparable to the "old" ones. For a small subset of equal-magnitude systems, there are some extra problems. There are more aspects to these problems than have been investigated so far (especially, the grid-iteration for the primary position also gets difficult), but the preliminary conclusion is that the reduction schemes envisaged by Lindegren in NDAC/LO/090 should be modified at the preprocessing stage. The modifications do not increase the processing

time significantly, and they will help avoid an "unnecessary" rms-increase for several hundred equal-magnitude binaries. (The IFOV-profile gives an rms-increase of similar magnitude and for a similar number of systems with separations 15-25 arcsec, but this is inherent in the instrument, and can not be avoided by changes in the reduction process).